

PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE FORMATION OF SOCIAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Nazirova Guzal Malikovna

Associate professor of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6628433>

Annotation. The child's personal and socio-psychological preparation for school is the formation of his readiness for new forms of communication, a new social position - the position of the student. The position of the student, in comparison with the situation of the preschool educator, requires the child to follow new rules for him, which are related to another position in society. This personal readiness is reflected in the child's unique attitude towards school, teacher and learning activities, peers, relatives, and himself.

Keywords: Social consciousness, preschool older children, child's behavior, child's psychological readiness, communicative competence, social authority, language skills.

Attitude towards school is determined by a child's willingness or unwillingness to follow the rules of the school regime, arrive on time for classes, and complete learning tasks at school and at home.

Attitudes toward the teacher and learning activities are determined by the child's perception of the different situations in the lesson in which direct emotional connections are excluded when it is not possible to speak on external topics. After you raise your hand, you need to ask questions on the topic.

Relationships with peers develop successfully if the child has personal characteristics such as conversation, the ability to give way in situations that require it. It is important for the child to be able to interact with other children, to be a member of the children's community.

Relationships with family and friends. As teaching becomes a child's main activity, relatives should view the future school student and his or her teaching as a more important, meaningful activity than a preschooler's play. A child who has a personal space in the family should feel the respectful attitude of relatives towards his or her new student role.

Attitudes, abilities, activities and their consequences. Appropriate self-assessment of the child allows him to quickly adapt to the new social conditions of the school. Excessive self-esteem can lead to a wrong reaction to a teacher's comments, resulting in "bad school," "bad teacher," and so on.

When preparing a child for school, he should be taught the following:

- communication rules;
- ability to communicate with peers and adults;
- ability to control their behavior without aggression;
- Ability to quickly adapt to a new environment.

To check your child's readiness for school, you should carefully monitor the child's behavior during any play in accordance with the rules in the presence of several peers or adults (lotto, developmental games, etc.). During the game you can see the following:

- whether the child follows the rules of the game;
- how to make connections;
- is considered a partner with others;
- able to control their own behavior;
- requires benefits from partners;
- Did the game fail?

One of the most important considerations in a child's social and personal development is the crisis 7 years. The seven signs of separation are the 7-year crisis, on the basis of which the child needs social recognition:

1. Negativism - not wanting to do anything just what an adult suggests.
2. Perseverance is not because he wants to, but because he demands it.
3. Eating - a child's behavior is directed against the norms of behavior imposed on him by adults.
4. Self-will is the desire for independence, the desire to do it yourself.
5. Protest Riot - actions in the form of protest (war against the outside world).
6. Depreciation - manifests itself in adults and what I love.
7. Despotism is the desire to show power over others.

How to overcome the 7-year crisis?

- It is important to remember that crises are temporary and will pass.
- The reason for the acute phase of the crisis is the difference between the parent's attitude and the child's desires and abilities requirements. It is therefore important to think about the validity of the prohibitions and the possibility of giving the child more freedom and independence.
- Pay more attention to the child's thoughts, opinions; try to understand it.
- The tone of a command or edit at this age is ineffective, so try to convince, reason, and analyze the possible consequences of his actions, not by forcing the child.

The most effective way to influence learning is to positively assess the child as an individual. Follow a set of rules when communicating with a child who is there with an adult:

1. Demonstration of friendly and understanding relationships ("I know you've tried a lot", etc.)
2. Mistakes made during the assignment or violation of the rules of conduct are made "here and now" taking into account the child's previous labor ("But now you made a mistake by pressing Masha").
3. Timely analysis of the causes of mistakes and bad behavior ("It looks like Masha pushed you first, but she didn't do it on purpose")
4. Discuss with the child the mistakes and acceptable forms of behavior in such a situation.
5. Believing he'll succeed ("I'm sure you won't push girls anymore")
6. Never miss an opportunity to tell your child you love him.

When there is no reaction on the part of the child to the actions, actions, words of the parents, the child cannot compare his behavior with that of the adult, i.e. he understands which behaviors are approved and which ones are wrong. . The child falls into an uncertain situation, his solution is completely motionless. The uniformity of the adult's reactions to the child's actions leads to the same result.

How a child reacts to mistakes depends on the attitude of the parent. If parents trust their child and rejoice in his or her insignificant success, then he or she will conclude that he or she is vital in the activity he or she is mentoring. If every failure of a child is perceived by the parents as a catastrophe, he is reconciled to his own uselessness. It is very important to be very careful about a child's actions and look for a reason to praise and approve even in the trivial.

A child's psychological readiness for school can be defined as a certain level of mental development that a child needs to attend school. It is also important to pay attention to the multi-component nature of this training. In the psychological literature devoted to the analysis of school maturity, the following elements of psychological preparation are most often named: intellectual, personal, and strong-willed. To date, a number of psychodiagnostic methods have been developed to determine a child's readiness for school (Wenger L.A., Witzlak G., Gutkina N.I., Kravtsova E.E., etc.). For example, in techniques developed by Wenger L.A. (2), Gutkina N.I. (3), great emphasis is placed on components of school maturity, such as mental development, fine motor skills, and personal training, mainly to a motivational level. Apparently, this is probably explained by the fact that the level of intellectual development, the level of coordination of the hand is easier to study the psychological technique, to determine the level of its formation.

Preparing for a personal "measurement" is much harder, although no one can deny its importance and significance. According to various researchers, 15 to 40 percent of elementary school students have a disability. One of the reasons for this situation is called the child's personal unpreparedness for school, where reading refers to the collective nature of the lesson. Therefore, the prospective student should have a number of skills such as communicating with adults and peers, finding their place in the children's group; know certain norms and rules of behavior and communication; the ability to accurately assess their actual and potential capabilities (the ability to self-assess). The greatest difficulties are, as a rule, experienced by children who do not attend kindergarten, are limited to adults with close social circle, and the experience of joint activities and communication with peers is insignificant. The next stage of the work is the development and testing of specific psychodiagnostic methods to study the child's personal readiness for school, as well as the cycle of developmental activities. This article provides a theoretical analysis of this component of school maturity. To reveal the content of personal preparation, it is necessary to refer to the concept of personality, the main personal neoplasms of preschool age.

An analysis of the psychological literature shows that there are different definitions of personality, each of which focuses on one aspect of personal development. Apparently, it will be difficult to give a definition that can be accepted by many psychologists of different schools and directions. The situation with the concept of 'person' encourages us to give the most appropriate

definition needed in this case to meaningfully complement the concept of personal readiness. The limitation of such a definition may lead to a number of objections, but in the context of solving specific problems, this is inevitable because infinity is incomprehensible. In our work, we adhere to the following concept as a systemic quality of the individual that is part of social relations. The formation of this quality occurs in the process of joint action and communication of the child with adults and peers, in the process of socialization and education.

For the person himself, the person works like his image-I, I-concept. The formation of a child's personality begins at preschool age. Throughout play, as a leading activity in preschool, the child experiences a variety of social roles and learns to obey the rules of their actions. It helps to distinguish two plans of his I-image in the child's mind - I am real and I am ideal. The older preschool educator has sufficient self-assessment skills based on the assessment of the child's behavior by adults. It can be imagined that if there is no difference between the image-I plans described above, the child will have difficulty in perceiving the requirements for him in the learning process, as well as in following him and evaluating the results of his actions. Perhaps in addition to the motivational component of personal preparation, we can add the following - the level of development of self-awareness, which is associated with stratified perception of the image.

Socio-psychological preparation can be distinguished as an integral part of school development or as one of the elements of personal preparation, because the study of the development of the child's personality outside the social or, more precisely, socio-cultural context fully reflects the content of such a complex concept dargumon. The lack of analysis of the socio-psychological component of school maturity is probably due to the position of social and youth psychologists. The research interests of the former are mainly in children, from adolescence to adulthood. The second, in turn, ignores the child's first steps in understanding the social environment, finding his or her place in society, and the mechanisms by which the child creates his or her own social image.

The following substructures can be distinguished in the socio-psychological structure of personal training:

- communicative competence,
- social authority;

- language skills.

The use of the concept of perfection is explained by its low application in child psychology. Therefore, in this way, differences in its interpretation can be avoided. The word "authority" means to understand something. Therefore, social competence is the knowledge of the norms and rules of behavior adopted in a particular socio-cultural environment, the attitude to them; apply this knowledge in practice.

But we return to the problem of shaping a child's personality in preschool. One of the major neoplasms of this century should be called the subordination of motives. According to Leontyev's figurative expression, in preschool childhood the first "nodes" of a person are connected in the process of interpersonal relationships, which is associated with the emergence of a hierarchy of motives. The extreme importance of this neoplasm has led to the fact that in the research of Russian psychologists dealing with the problems of child readiness for school, personal preparation has fallen into a motivational state. Enough for other personal neoplasms, such as the development of self-awareness and self-awareness, the desire and ability to cooperate, the understanding of their social "I", the emergence of the first sketch contour of children's inseparable worldview, and so on. ignored.

In the preschool age, the child's new socially significant activity - the system of learning-related needs - is shaping the child's inner position. The process of emergence of the inner position of the student can create the necessary conditions for the subsequent formation of social identity in the child, ie. handing over by the child himself to a certain group - schoolchildren. Formation is a process, in this case identification, the result of which is identity - personal or social. The most important step in the process of acquiring a child's social identity is to start school, his or her direct entry into the social environment, he or she has a certain image formed as a result of adult school and reading stories. The child has the opportunity to act in this new social situation for him.

References

1. Ravshanbek, J. (2022). CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM, ITS BASIC PRINCIPLES AND FEATURES. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(4), 304-309.
2. O'G'Li, J. R. M. (2022). METHODS OF ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT STUDY OF STUDENTS IN THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM. *Ta'lim fidoyilari*, 25(5), 93-97.

3. Jorayev, N. S. (2021, July). QUALITY LEARNING PROCESS-AS A MECHANICAL SUM OF TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESSES. In Euro-Asia Conferences (pp. 57-59).
4. Sadullayevich, J. N. (2021). Improving psychological technologies for the development of professional reflection in future teachers. ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL, 11(1), 229-232.
5. Джураева, М. А. (2022, May). ПРИЁМЫ КОНТРОЛЯ УРОВНЯ ЗНАНИЙ НА УРОКАХ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА И ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 28-32).
6. Abdukakhhorovna, Z. M. (2022). Lexical Polysemy of the Russian Language. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 22, 77-81.
7. Akilovna, E. M. (2022). METHODS OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGUES. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(05), 228-232.
8. Akilovna, E. M., & Fotima, B. (2022). MODERN APPROACHES TO CHILDREN'S INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENT. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(05), 233-237.
9. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2017). Бағрикенглик ижтимоий-фалсафий қадрият. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 27-28.
10. МИРАХМЕДОВ, Ж. М., & БАБАЕВА, Н. М. (2016). К ВОПРОСУ О СУЩНОСТИ СОЦИОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ. In Будущее науки-2016 (pp. 16-19).
11. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2016). Некоторые аспекты проблемных концепций осмысления динамики научного знания. In Молодежь и наука: реальность и будущее (pp. 245-247).
12. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2017). Тарих фалсафий тадқиқот предмети сифатида. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 26-27.
13. Мирахмедов, Ж. М. (2016). Теоретическая подготовка студентов к социологическим исследованиям в практической и самостоятельной работе. In Молодежь и наука: реальность и будущее (pp. 318-319).